

INVESTIGATION INTO THE UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY BEFORE, DURING AND AFTER EXAMINATION PERIOD AMONG NCE STUDENTS OF KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION ILORIN

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Abstract

The study examined the utilization of library before, during and after examination period by students in Kwara state college of education Ilorin. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select 250 respondents from 2,877 registered library users between 2020-2022 while all copies of the questionnaire were retrieved. The analysis of data was based on Simple Frequency Percentage and Average Weighted Response Findings revealed that NCE students use library most during the examination. Most respondents used the library to prepare for examinations despite the fact that college library have a lot of benefits for regular utilization by the students. Factors like insufficient information resources, inadequate awareness of the available information resources and lack of electronic information resources hinder the utilization of the college library. Recommendations were made to improve the utilization of library by NCE students.

Introduction

The importance of libraries in the Higher Institution in Nigeria Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. Library is associated with education while education is a societal instrument of change which consequently, affects the educational, sociological, political, economical, scientific and technological changes. Onaolapo (2016) stated that academic libraries serve as the fulcrum which the intellectual activities of tertiary institutions hinge on. Without the existence of academic library stocked with varieties of relevant information resources and manned by the professionals in the field of librarianship in tertiary institution, education will not be complete and largely defective. Academic library is a vital tool that helps every student most especially in colleges of education to fulfill obligation and to achieve their academic goals. The academic libraries services in the colleges of education helps the institutions to attain their objectives of training the students to become the future teachers “manpower required for the development of nations” The Colleges of education libraries are among the academic libraries which contribute immensely to the development of Nigeria.

The utilization of library is very important to students in colleges of education for their

academic achievements. The method of teaching adopted in Nigerian colleges of education is not only about students taking notes and regurgitating the lecturers' notes during a class test or examination. Meanwhile, students in colleges of education are members of the college community admitted for various educational courses. Students enrolled into the colleges of education purposely to be equipped with the methodology and skills of teaching in Pre-primary/Nursery, Primary and Junior Secondary level of education. Hence, accessibility to library information resources in different formats becomes a prerequisite to satisfy their information requirements through the use of their college libraries. Quadri, Adetimirin and Idowu (2014), explained that it is imperative for undergraduates to have their information requirements met, which will enhance and promote their academic careers and also satisfy their psychological and social needs. The main objective of funding colleges of education libraries is to readily make available appropriate library resources that are adequate, which could be in non-print and print formats. These resources are to enrich the students in their class assignment, micro-teaching and teaching practice exercise and completing their project work by making

provision for adequate and appropriate information resources and services, which could enhance their academic achievements.

Ogunmodede, Adio and Odunola (2011) explained that academic libraries provide both resources and services for their clientele. The services provided by college libraries include: reference services, lending services, referral services, selective dissemination of information services (SDI), photocopy services and library instruction services (Adeeko 2021). The information resources in the library are the materials, which assist the college libraries to perform their functions efficiently. These include print (books, periodicals, government publications, graphics, maps and atlas) and electronic resources. Based on this resources, the library should build its services and the overall functioning of the library for it to remain a place of interest to users. This is because the bar is continually raised as improved services soon become the norm and the minimum expected. Services should be always lifted to meet the ever changing tastes and expectations of users. Kiilu and Otikey (2016) revealed that undergraduate information seeking behaviour shows most students do not use the library effectively. They showed poor information seeking habit despite the well-equipped library available in tertiary institution, it was observed that students, using it were very few.

Therefore, it is imperatives to investigate the of utilization period and identify the causes students to decide to dedicate their leisure period or not to utilize various resources available library. What can library management do to encourage the library utilization period of students in colleges of education. The purpose of this study is to get a deeper understanding of the colleges of Education students information seeking process from start to finish, and identify factors that influence library utilization period. Obasuyi (2020) stated that Utilization period of academic libraries is still an issue in many campuses and it is the expectation of College Librarians all over the world most importantly in Nigeria yearning that their libraries are not adequately utilized by its numerous clientele. To this end, efforts should be made by the College libraries to provide educational resources and services targeted at meeting the academic, social and recreational needs to the

expected users. Library as the academic nerve center of the higher institution should be able to meet up with its mandate in supporting the academic, social, innovative and learning processes in the colleges of education. College libraries play crucial roles to support educational activities of undergraduates in the university. Therefore, there is need to develop effective strategies for attracting the students to use the library. Olofinsawe and Oyeniya (2010) affirmed that academic libraries have to build strong collection of information resources in physical and digital format to cater for knowledge requirements of their users.

Objectives of the study

- Examine the period the NCE students in College of education Ilorin use library most
- Investigate the purposes for the utilization of library by NCE students in College of education Ilorin
- Expose the NCE students in College of education Ilorin the benefit from the utilization of library resources
- Examine the problems facing the utilization of library resources by NCE students in Kwara state college of Education Ilorin.
- Suggest measures that can influence the NCE students in Kwara State College of Education Ilorin in the utilization of library resources.

Research Questions

- ❖ What period does the students in College of Education Ilorin use the library?
- ❖ What are the purposes for the use of library by NCE students in Kwara State College of Education Ilorin?
- ❖ What are the benefits the NCE students in College of education Ilorin derived from the regular utilization of the college Library?
- ❖ What are the problems facing the utilization of the College Library by NCE students in Kwara state college of Education Ilorin?
- ❖ What are the measures that can influence the regular utilization of College Library by the students of Kwara State College of Education Ilorin?

Hypothesis for the study

H₀ = There is no significant difference between the College library and the utilization period of the students in Kwara State College of Education Ilorin.

Review of Related Literature

Bashir (2017) opined that libraries are one of the important segments of any academic institution that work as center of information resources and services. They provide a number of opportunities of research, learning and recreation to an academic community. Students usually consult libraries for academic purposes and such information-seeking behavior promotes academic excellence in students. Though, students utilize different channels and resources to collect information such as the internet, colleagues, libraries, friends, family members, etc. Libraries in colleges of education works as a service organization which equipped the students and staff with the required information for their academic achievement. Library as a facility that comprises items and materials that can be accessed for the extraction of information from a specified location which includes the storage mediums of such information. Library services are the offer of information and information facilities to the end users for various purposes in different forms (mediums) and means (delivery mode).

Mogaka (2019) defines a library as a building or room in which a collection of books, journals, articles, newspapers, and tapes are kept for people to read study or borrow. A library plays a very important role in the teaching learning process. It is a service which is very essential in the education sector. The education process worldwide cannot function without books. The main function of the library in the colleges of education is to avail all books, periodicals and other reading materials to the student and staff in the institution at their convenience. College library provides to the student's materials which are of interest and value to them to compliment their lectures and widening their knowledge in the field of their studies. Library in the colleges of education has seen as inevitable to the academic achievement in the institution. Students who often use the library indicate better performance in examination than those who fail to make use of the

library. Therefore, students need to be aware of the benefits from regular utilization of the library as a key to the academic achievement and accomplishment of a great success at all levels of education. Library helps students to develop good study habits for the purpose of reading for leisure, to pass examinations and to obtain information on different aspects of life.

It is very important for the college library to expose the students in colleges of education to the benefit that could be derived while visiting the library regularly. Dada (2016) stated that academic libraries provide access to enjoyable and information rich reading materials through which the students can gain and improve their skills. Regular visit of the library can lead to higher student achievement. To achieve education pursuance in colleges of education without college library being involved would be very difficult. It should provide adequate services and information materials in all formats for their students to support them in their educational activities. The business of academic libraries is the acquisition, organization, dissemination and preservation of information to support the curriculum of the school. The academic library has to provide sufficiently, good resources to complement qualitative education. These resources can take polytechnics students' far above technical literacy and developing their reading habit which makes permanent literacy attainable.

Obasuyi, (2020) opined Utilization of academic libraries is still an issue in many campuses and it is the expectation of College Librarians in the world over that their libraries are adequately utilized by its numerous clientele. To this end, efforts are being made by the college libraries to provide educational resources and services targeted at meeting the academic, social and recreational needs to the expected users. This is against the background that the Library as the academic nerve center of colleges of education should be able to meet up with its mandate in supporting the academic, social, innovative and learning processes in the college. College libraries play crucial roles to support educational activities of National Certificate education (NCE) and affiliated students in the college. Therefore, there is need to develop effective strategies for attracting the students towards the utilization

library. Utilization of the library is one way the library can demonstrate its usefulness and relevance in our campuses. Utilization of the Library will influence students' academic performances and achievements if adequate resources and services are provided.

According to Gbemi-Ogunleye, (2016) the utilization of library by students is a sine qua non. Utilization of the library and its' resources has been a consequence of several factors. Some factors are users based; some are institutional, environmental, and technological while some are library centered. These factors are expected to be factored in by the Management of any library when developing their products and services. The primary objective of college of education library is to provide adequate learning resources and services to satisfy the information requirements of staff and students in line with the mandate of the colleges of education. subjects, including pamphlets and audio visual materials.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study population comprises 2,877 registered library users between 2020-2022

out of which 250 respondents were selected using stratified random sampling technique. Questionnaire was the data collection instrument used. The analysis of data collected was based on Simple Frequency Percentage and Average Weighted Response.

Analysis of Data

Table 1: Distribution and return rate of the questionnaire

Result

The socio status of the students in the study area.

SEX:are the biological traits that societies use to assign people into the category of either male or female, whether it be through a focus on chromosomes, genitalia, or some other physical ascription.

AGE: refers to the hierarchical ranking of people into age groups within a society.

Table 1 present the result of the socio status of the students in the study area. The result showed that 85% of the sampled students are female while 15% are males. On age 50% were 20 years and below, 40% between the ages of 21 to 23 years and 105 24 years above.

Table 1: Socio status of the students Demography of Respondent

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	64	26%
Female	186	74%
Total	250	100%
Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	94	38%
20-30	135	54%
30 and above	21	8%
Total	250	100
Educational Level		
N C E 1	64	26%
N C E 2	107	43%
N C E 3	79	31%
Total	250	100

Table 1 present the result of the socio status of the students in the study area. The result showed that 74% of the sampled students are female while 24% are males. On age 38% were 20 years and below, 54% between the ages of 20 to 30 years and 8% are 30 years above. Similarly, on the

educational level 26% are NCE I, 43% NCE II and 31% NCE III respectively. The implication of this result is that females are more likely use the library than males. The NCE II students seek more for knowledge in the library.

Table 2 The period the students use the College Library most

Items	S A	A	D	S D	W/SUM	FREQ	AWR
1	97 (338)	102 (306)	36 (72)	15(15)	731	250	2.9
2	228 (912)	17 (51)	2 (4)	03 (3)	970	250	3.9
3	79 (316)	84 (252)	56 (112)	31 (31)	711	250	2.8
4	78 (312)	163 (504)	07 (14)	02 (2)	832	250	3.3
TAWR	1,878	1,113	202	51	3,244	1,000	3.2

Table 2 above showed that the total average weighted response (TAWR) is 3.2 which fall within 3.01 – 5, Therefore, the result above indicate that majority of students are using college library mostly during examination period. Though the result revealed that the NCE students in the college of education use the college library before during and after the examination period but they make use of the library mostly during the

examination. This agrees with the result of Ossai-Onah, Anyanwu, & Obichere, (2012) who observed that despite the importance of academic library to the students, it has become obvious that students in the higher institution in Nigeria are no longer read. They only read when they have examination to write, outside that, reading has no meaning to them.

Table 3: The purpose for the use of College Library by NCE students in Kwara State College of Education Ilorin

Items	S A	A	D	S D	W/Sum	Freq.	AWR
5.	72 (288)	86 (258)	53 (106)	39 (39)	691	250	2.8
6.	227 (908)	18 (54)	02 (4)	03 (3)	969	250	3.9
7.	86 (344)	75 (225)	82 (164)	17 (17)	750	250	3.0
8.	64 (256)	59 (177)	76 (152)	71 (71)	656	250	2.6
TAWR	2,588	828	450	132	3,066	1,000	3.1

Table 3 above showed that the total average weighted response (TAWR) is 3.1 which fall within 3.01 – 5, Therefore, the result above indicate that majority of students are using the library mostly to prepare for examination Though, the results revealed that students in the college of education utilized the library to read library

textbooks, for recreational services and for research activities, but mainly they use the college library to prepare for examinations. This agrees with the result of Bahatti, Batoool and Malik (2013) whose submitted that most students predominantly used the library as a place to study for examination and to complete their assignment.

Table 4: The benefit the NCE students in College of education Ilorin could derived from the regular utilization of the college Library?

Items	S A	A	D	S D	W/SUM	FREQ	AWR
9.	178 (712)	62 (186)	08 (16)	02 (2)	916	250	3.6
10.	153 (612)	54 (162)	33 (66)	10 (10)	850	250	3.4
11.	230 (920)	13 (39)	3 (3)	04 (4)	966	250	3.9
12.	192 (768)	43 (129)	09 (18)	06 (6)	921	250	3.7
TAWR	3,012	516	103	22	3,653	1,000	3.7

Table 4 above showed that the total average weighted response (TAWR) is 3.7 which fall within 3.01 – 5, Therefore, the result above indicate that majority of students agreed that NCE students could derive a lot of benefits while using the College Library regularly. The result revealed that NCE students will be enriched in knowledge, get prepared against future challenges, assists by

assessing the textbooks they cannot afford to buy, and get inculcated with the habit of reading. This agrees with the result of Afolabi (2014) who stated that the role that is played and meant to be played by the academic library makes it to stand out as place where the students can enrich their knowledge and prepare themselves against future challenges.

Table 5: Problems affecting the library utilization by NCE students in College of Education Ilorin

Items	S A	A	D	S D	W/SUM	FREQ	AWR
13	178 (712)	62 (186)	08 (16)	02 (2)	916	250	3.6
14	153 (612)	54 (162)	33 (66)	10 (10)	850	250	3.4
15	117 (468)	83 (249)	23 (46)	27 (27)	788	250	3.2
16	230 (920)	09 (27)	07 (14)	04 (4)	920	250	3.7
TAWR	2,712	624	142	43	3,474	1,000	3.5

Table 5 above showed that the total average weighted response (TAWR) is 3.5 which fall within 3.01 – 5, Therefore, the result above indicate that majority of students agreed that there are problems militating against the utilization of College Library in NCE in the Kwara State College of Education Ilorin. The result revealed that insufficient books in the college library, lack of regular awareness on the resources and services of the library, negative attitudes of the staff of college library, and lack of electronics resources affects the utilization of the college library by

NCE students in Kwara State College of Education Ilorin. This result is in line with Kiilu and Otike (2016) whose stated that leading reasons for infrequent or non-use of academic library resources have been identified to include the lack of awareness, perceived lack of relevance, lack of time, distance, lack of skills in the use of electronic resources, having personal books and/or borrowing books from friends, access to the internet from home as well as borrowing from other libraries, no need and denied use.

Table 6: Measures that can influence utilization of library by NCE students in College of Education Ilorin

Items	S A	A	D	S D	W/SUM	FREQ	AWR
17	189 (756)	57 (171)	04 (8)	02 (2)	937	250	3.7
18	236 (944)	10 (30)	03 (6)	01 (1)	981	250	3.9
19	228 (912)	16 (48)	05 (10)	01 (1)	971	250	3.9
20	176 (704)	57 (171)	13 (26)	04 (4)	905	250	3.6
TAWR	4,192	498	52	11	4,753	1,250	3.8

Table 5 above showed that the total average weighted response (TAWR) is 3.5 which fall within 3.01 – 5, Therefore, the result above indicates that there are measures that influence utilization of library by NCE students in College of Education Ilorin. The result revealed that When College Library acquire more relevant books, do more awareness on the library resources and services available in the library, engages the staff to improve their services, and provides electronics resources, the NCE students will make use of library more than ever before. This result is in line

with Omelozu and Ogo (2018) whose stated that the academic libraries in Nigeria should create awareness of available of information resources in the library (both on the shelves within the library and on the database) and serves as agent of independent learning promotion.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The major findings were that students make use the college library mostly during examination period. Though, student make use of the library before and after examination to enrich their

knowledge and for recreational purpose. The student derives benefits while using the library to enrich their knowledge, prepare them against future challenges, assists them by assessing the textbooks they cannot afford to buy, and get inculcated with the habit of reading. Therefore, it was concluded that the students utilize the library resources more during the examination period than before and after examination period. Based on the foregoing, the following recommendations were made: College libraries should engage in promotional strategies such as book talk, display and exhibition, and current awareness services to improve the utilization of the libraries by NCE students; College libraries should provide functional electronics resources as an urgent need for college library and internet facilities in the library to improve the utilization of the libraries by NCE students; The funding to college libraries should be increased in order to enable them acquire more relevant information resources to meet the rising needs of the needs of NCE students.

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